

ID	Name	X_WGS	Y_WGS	Hap 1 / CcH01	Hap 2 / CcH135	Hap 3 / CcH79	Hap 4 / CcH71	Hap 5	Hap 6	Hap 7	Hap 8	Hap 9	Hap 10 / CcH26	Hap 11 / CcH219	Hap 12 / CcH26	Hap 13 / CcH216	Hap 14	Hap 15	Hap 16	Hap 17	Hap 18	Hap 19	Hap 20	Hap 21 / CcH196	Hap 22	Hap 23	Hap 24	Hap 25	Hap 26	Hap 27 / CcH41	suma
	Clade			Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	
1	Dorset/Wilts	-2,32682	50,73731	7	28		8																								43
2	Somerset	-3,46415	50,7513		19																										19
3	Berks	-1,13252	51,44606		2		7	10																							19
4	Norfolk	0,891402	52,62085			41																									41
5	Moray	-3,38116	57,5223				2	2		12				2	3	3	2	2							1						29
6	Perth	-3,43846	56,39307					7	4	13	7			1	2									1							35
7	Ayr	-4,597	55,43591					40							4					2											50
8	N York	-1,06986	53,95013					20		3																1					24
9	Durham	-1,58135	54,77558					7		5																1					13
10	Carlisle	-2,93361	54,89188					25		1													1								28
11	Lancs	-2,72592	53,78047					4					4	2							1	1									12
suma				7	49	41	17	115	4	34	7	2	4	2	3	9	3	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	

ID	Name	X_WGS	Y_WGS	Central	East	West
1	Dorset/Wilts	-2,32682	50,73731	43		
2	Somerset	-3,46415	50,7513	19		
3	Berks	-1,13252	51,44606	19		
4	Norfolk	0,891402	52,62085	41		
5	Moray	-3,38116	57,5223	29		
6	Perth	-3,43846	56,39307	35		
7	Ayr	-4,597	55,43591	50		
8	N York	-1,06986	53,95013	24		
9	Durham	-1,58135	54,77558	13		
10	Carlisle	-2,93361	54,89188	28		
11	Lancs	-2,72592	53,78047	12		
				313		

ID	Name	X_WGS	Y_WGS	N indiv.	N haplot.	N pol sites	Hapl. Div. (Hd)	Nucl. Div. (rt)	Aver. n of pair. Diff. (k)
1	Dorset/Wilts	-2,32682	50,73731	43	3				
2	Somerset	-3,46415	50,7513	19	1				
3	Berks	-1,13252	51,44606	19	3				
4	Norfolk	0,891402	52,62085	41	1				
5	Moray	-3,38116	57,5223	29	9				
6	Perth	-3,43846	56,39307	35	7				
7	Ayr	-4,597	55,43591	50	7				
8	N York	-1,06986	53,95013	24	3				
9	Durham	-1,58135	54,77558	13	3				
10	Carlisle	-2,93361	54,89188	28	4				
11	Lancs	-2,72592	53,78047	12	5				

ID	Name	X_WGS	Y_WGS	H12 / CcH10	H13 / CcH19	H16 / CcH6	H18 / CcH7	H23 / CcH188	H41 / CcH66	H48 / CcH26	H52 / CcH18	H68	B01 / CcH26	B02 / CcH7	B03 / CcH26	B04 / Cc19	B05	B06 / CcH126	B07 / CcH18	B08	B09 / CcH7	B10	B11 / CcH7	B12 / CcH6	H15	H40	H43	B13	B14	B15	B16	B17	B18	B19	B20	B21	B22	B23			
				Central	Central	East	Central	East	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	East	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central			
1	Arezzo	11,88	43,46313	10	46							1	1					2	5	1	1	1			14					1											
2	Pisa	10,68657	43,08208		3		17	1																		17		14	1												
3	Parma	10,45041	44,6105		6	8	12			4				1	2	1										31		6	1	1	1		6		1	1					
4	Grosetto	11,15523	42,75976						1		1															14	1	1												1	1
suma				10	55	8	29	1	1	4	10	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	76	1	15	7	1	1	2	6	1	1	1	1	1	1		

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81
79
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C. c. italicus

ID	Name	X_WGS	Y_WGS	Central	East	West
1	Arezzo	11,88	43,46313	60		
2	Pisa	10,68657	43,08208	49	1	
3	Parma	10,45041	44,6105	39	9	
4	Grosetto	11,15523	42,75976	2		
				150	10	

ID	Name	X_WGS	Y_WGS	N indiv.	N haplot.	N pol sites	Hapl. Div. (Hd)	Nucl. Div. (π)	Aver. n of pair. Diff. (k)
1	Arezzo	11,88	43,46313	74	7				
2	Pisa	10,68657	43,08208	81	16				
3	Parma	10,45041	44,6105	79	17				
4	Grosetto	11,15523	42,75976	18	5				

ID	Name	X_WGS	Y_WGS	H01	H02	H03	H04	H05	H06	H07	H08	H09	H10	H11	H12	H13	H14	H15	H16	H17	H18	H19	H20	H21	H22	H23	H24	H25	H26	H27	H28	H29	H30	H31	suma
Clade				West	West	West	West	West	Central	East	Central	West	Celtic-iberian	Celtic-iberian	Celtic-iberian	Celtic-iberian	Central	Celtic-iberian	Central	Central	Central	East	Central	West	Celtic-iberian	West	Central	Central	Central	West	Central	Celtic-iberian	Central	Celtic-iberian	
1	Western Asturias (As)	-5,74658	43,06747												6	2	2		1					4	3	2									20
2	Bordeaux (Bo)	-0,65944	44,52710					4	1	3	2																								10
3	Cadiz (Ca)	-6,13563	36,48794	1	6	7	1																												15
4	Centre (Ce)	-4,43283	40,51828			5						2																		5	1	1			14
5	Galicia (Ga)	-7,92523	42,29577										3	1	2	1	2	1																	10
6	Lleida (Le)	0,57382	41,39968																1	1	3	1	4												10
7	Picos de Europa (PI)	-4,78326	43,04264									1	2													1	3	1	1						10
8	Soria(So)	-2,48673	41,59057																												7				10
9	Sueve (Su)	-5,35575	43,46163									2	5			2																	1		10
suma				1	6	12	1	4	1	3	2	5	10	1	8	3	7	1	5	1	3	1	4	4	3	2	1	3	1	1	5	8	1	1	109

ID	Name	X_WGS	Y_WGS	Central	East	West	Celtic-iberian
1	Western Asturias (As)	-5,74658	43,06747	3		6	11
2	Bordeaux (Bo)	-0,65944	44,52710	3	3	4	
3	Cadiz (Ca)	-6,13563	36,48794				15
4	Centre (Ce)	-4,43283	40,51828	6		7	1
5	Galicia (Ga)	-7,92523	42,29577	2			8
6	Lleida (Le)	0,57382	41,39968	9	1		
7	Picos de Europa (PI)	-4,78326	43,04264	6		2	2
8	Soria(So)	-2,48673	41,59057	3			7
9	Sueve (Su)	-5,35575	43,46163	2		2	5
				34	4	36	34

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ID	Name	X_WGS	Y_WGS	N indiv.	N haplot.	N pol sites	Hapl. Div. (Hd)	Nucl. Div. (r)	Aver. n of pair. Diff. (k)
1	Western Asturias (As)	-5,74658	43,06747	20	7		0,35	0,013	
2	Bordeaux (Bo)	-0,65944	44,52710	10	4		0,4	0,008	
3	Cadiz (Ca)	-6,13563	36,48794	15	4		0,27	0,007	
4	Centre (Ce)	-4,43283	40,51828	14	5		0,36	0,008	
5	Galicia (Ga)	-7,92523	42,29577	10	6		0,6	0,009	
6	Lleida (Le)	0,57382	41,39968	10	5		0,5	0,005	
7	Picos de Europa (PI)	-4,78326	43,04264	10	7		0,7	0,012	
8	Soria(So)	-2,48673	41,59057	10	2		0,2	0,002	
9	Sueve (Su)	-5,35575	43,46163	10	4		0,4	0,01	
							0,28	0,012	

ID	Name	X_WGS	Y_WGS	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L6	L7 / CcH187	L8	L9	L10	L11 / CcH19	L12 / CcH10	L13	L14 / CcH66	L15 / CcH66	L16	L17 / CcH26	L18 / CcH79	L19 / CcH6	L20 / CcH188	L21 / CcH89	L22	L23 / CcH153	L24 / CcH184	suma
Clade				A2	A2	A2	A2	A2	A2	A3	A3	A3	A3	A1	A1	A1	A3	A3	A3	A3	A3	B	B	B	B	B	B	
				<i>C. c. italicus</i>	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	Central	East	East	East	East	East	East						
1	Orsomaso (OM)	15,93157	39,72842	1	21						2	1	1			1												27
2	Castelporziano (CP)	12,42059	41,70484			22																						22
3	Sienna (SI)	11,32250	43,28739				1	6									1	1										9
4	Grosetto (GR)	11,14003	42,77351					7																		1		8
5	Massa (MS)	10,14768	44,02636					8																				8
6	Foresta Umbra (FU)	15,99769	41,79502						1																			1
7	Forli (FO)	12,06683	44,18689							2				2														4
8	Majella National Park (MJ)	14,09486	42,05916							2															2			4
9	Arezzo (AR)	11,87084	43,43877											1														1
10	Florence (FL)	11,25731	43,76859											1														1
11	Roccagiovine (RG)	12,90650	42,04348												2													2
12	Trento (TN)	11,12917	46,04295																1		1	3	3					8
13	Sondrio (SO)	9,88637	46,13612																	1	1	1	1					4
14	Liguria (LI)	8,40384	44,28550																				1		1			2
suma				1	21	22	1	21	1	4	2	1	1	4	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	4	4	1	2	1	1	101

ID	Name	X_WGS	Y_WGS	Central	East	West	C. c. italicus
1	Orsomaso (OM)	15,93157	39,72842	5			22
2	Castelporziano (CP)	12,42059	41,70484				22
3	Sienna (SI)	11,32250	43,28739	2			7
4	Grosetto (GR)	11,14003	42,77351		1		7
5	Massa (MS)	10,14768	44,02636				8
6	Foresta Umbra (FU)	15,99769	41,79502				1
7	Forli (FO)	12,06683	44,18689	4			
8	Majella National Park (MJ)	14,09486	42,05916	2	2		
9	Arezzo (AR)	11,87084	43,43877	1			
10	Florence (FL)	11,25731	43,76859	1			
11	Roccagiovine (RG)	12,90650	42,04348	2			
12	Trento (TN)	11,12917	46,04295	2	6		
13	Sondrio (SO)	9,88637	46,13612	2	2		
14	Liguria (LI)	8,40384	44,28550				2
				21	13		67

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ID	Name	X_WGS	Y_WGS	N indiv.	N haplot.	N pol sites	Hapl. Div. (Hd)	Nucl. Div. (τ)	Aver. n of pair. Diff. (k)
1	Orsomaso (OM)	15,93157	39,72842	27	6				
2	Castelporziano (CP)	12,42059	41,70484	22	1				
3	Sienna (SI)	11,32250	43,28739	9	4				
4	Grosetto (GR)	11,14003	42,77351	8	2				
5	Massa (MS)	10,14768	44,02636	8	1				
6	Foresta Umbra (FU)	15,99769	41,79502	1	1				
7	Forli (FO)	12,06683	44,18689	4	2				
8	Majella National Park (MJ)	14,09486	42,05916	4	2				
9	Arezzo (AR)	11,87084	43,43877	1	1				
10	Florence (FL)	11,25731	43,76859	1	1				
11	Roccagiovine (RG)	12,90650	42,04348	2	1				
12	Trento (TN)	11,12917	46,04295	8	4				
13	Sondrio (SO)	9,88637	46,13612	4	4				
14	Liguria (LI)	8,40384	44,28550	2	2				
				101					